

AN ELASTO-PLASTIC MODEL TO PREDICT PERMANENT INDENTATION DUE TO IMPACT AND QUASI-STATIC INDENTATION ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a finite element model based on an anisotropic elasto-plastic theory was established to capture permanent indentations on composite laminates under low velocity impact and quasi-static indentation. The parameters in the anisotropic elasto-plastic theory were determined from the analysis results of a micromechanical model. As the reason for the knee-point on the curve of dent depth-impact energy, fiber break was considered in this model. Cohesive elements were used in interlaminar to simulate the damage of delamination. The numerical analysis was implemented by ABAQUS and the user-defined material subroutine VUMAT. Experimental and numerical studies on two kinds of laminates (T300/6421 and T700/6421) were carried out. The calculated results are coordinate with the tested results well. Results show that fiber breakage happens in the laminates of T300 instead of T700 when impact energy or contact force increases because there is a big difference between the T300 and T700 fibers observed by SEM. A comparison shows it is correlative between the QSI applied energy and the impact energy on T300 laminates. In conclusion, fiber breakage and the match between the fiber and matrix have a significant influence on the permanent indentation and damage behaviours.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are easily damaged from low-velocity impact such as dropped tools, impact of hail and stones, which will greatly reduce the strength of structure. In practice, the likely impact damage at the threshold of reliable detection has been called barely visible impact damage (BVID), and composite structures containing BVID are required to sustain the ultimate load [1]. Permanent indentation is the quantitative description of BVID due to the facility of measurement. Therefore, studies of permanent indentation become more and more important.

Permanent indentation is mainly caused by low-velocity impact or static indentation process. Over the years, many researches about low-velocity impact and quasi-static indentation on composite structures are focus on the evolution processes of multiple damage modes inside the laminates [2-5], few researchers have studied on permanent indentation. Experimentally, some researchers have got some important phenomena and conclusion from their studies [6-8], but the mechanisms of the formation for permanent indentation have not been totally clarified. Numerically, Liu et al. [9] used the Hertzian contact law to predict dent depth, but it could only be applied to predict the shallow dents when there are no severe damages happened. Some researchers [10, 11] used non-linear shear damage models to capture permanent indentation, but it was only a byproduct of their models to simulate the impact damage processes and needed more experimental verifications. Bouvet et al. [12, 13] had got permanent indentation using a “pseudo-plasticity” law which is qualitatively tested by three-point bending introduced in the matrix cracking elements, but it was inapplicable for high-impact energy with large permanent indentation when fibre failure happened inside.

The main purpose of this study is to establish a finite element model to predict permanent indentation due to low-velocity impact and QSI. To certify the validation of the model, impact and QSI tests on two material series (T300/6421 and T700/6421) were carried out. Experimental and numerical results and the comparison between them were presented in this paper.

2 THEORY AND APPROACH

2.1 Anisotropic elasto-plastic theory

The anisotropic elasto-plasticity theory developed by Sun et al. [15-18] is effect to predict the non-linear behavior of fiber-reinforced composites and it has been employed to impact simulation [14] and also adopted in this work.

The yield function proposed by Sun et al. is quadratic in stresses as follows:

$$2f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = a_{11}\sigma_{11}^2 + a_{22}\sigma_{22}^2 + a_{33}\sigma_{33}^2 + 2a_{12}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2a_{13}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33} + 2a_{23}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} + 2a_{44}\sigma_{12}^2 + 2a_{55}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{13}^2 = k \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, σ_{ij} is the stresses in principle material directions. Nine plasticity coefficients a_{ij} , which describe the amount of anisotropy in plasticity, are assumed to be constants. k is a state variable depending on the plastic strain.

As many experimental data show that fiber composite behaves linearly up to failure in the fiber direction and fibre reinforced composite materials are transversely isotropic, it is thus reasonable to assume that [15]:

$$a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = 0 \text{ and } a_{22} = a_{33} \quad (2)$$

Using the associated flow rule, incremental plastic (inelastic) strain can be written in terms of the plastic potential as

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$ is the plastic strain tensor, $d\lambda$ is a proportionality factor.

The increment of plastic work per unit volume is given by

$$dW^p = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = 2fd\lambda \quad (4)$$

An effective stress is defined as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{3f} \quad (5)$$

The increment effective plastic strain can be defined as

$$dW^p = \bar{\sigma} d\bar{\varepsilon}^p \quad (6)$$

The incremental strain can be decomposed linearly into the elastic part and plastic part

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \quad (7)$$

According to the incremental plastic theory, the incremental stress only depends on the incremental elastic strain, thus the incremental stress-strain relation can be written as

$$d\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}(d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the stiffness matrix.

A plastic modulus is needed to be defined as

$$H = \frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{d\bar{\varepsilon}^p} \quad (9)$$

From Eqs.(3)-(9), the relation between the plastic strain increment and the total strain increment can be derived

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \frac{(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}})^T \mathbf{C} d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{\frac{4}{9} \bar{\sigma}^2 H + (\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}})^T \mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \quad (10)$$

In plastic calculation, the plastic modulus should be given at all stress levels. In this work, a simple power law was adopted for the hardening law

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = A\bar{\sigma}^n \quad (11)$$

2.2 Determination of the plasticity parameters

Before the elasto-plastic calculation, 9 parameters of a_{ij} in Eq.(1) and coefficient A in Eq.(11) needed to be determined. Sun et al. proposed a method by micromechanical analysis to determine these parameters [16-18]. Fiber was assumed to be transversely isotropic and matrix was assumed to be isotropic in the model.

The associated flow rule of Eq.(3) can be written in form of component:

$$\{d\varepsilon^p\} = \begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{33}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{12}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{13}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{23}^p \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} a_{11}\sigma_{11} + a_{12}\sigma_{22} + a_{13}\sigma_{33} \\ a_{12}\sigma_{11} + a_{22}\sigma_{22} + a_{23}\sigma_{33} \\ a_{13}\sigma_{11} + a_{23}\sigma_{22} + a_{33}\sigma_{33} \\ 2a_{44}\sigma_{12} \\ 2a_{55}\sigma_{13} \\ 2a_{66}\sigma_{23} \end{Bmatrix} d\lambda \quad (12)$$

Before fiber break happens, the component $d\varepsilon_{11}^p$ equals zero due to the linear behavior in fiber direction [15].

Define the plastic poisson's ratio as

$$\nu_{ij}^p = -\frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}^p}{d\varepsilon_{ii}^p} \quad (13)$$

Eq.(13) is the definition of direction under uniaxial loading along i direction ($i, j=1,2,3$).

Thus the 6 coefficients corresponding to the normal stresses can be derived from Eqs.(12) and (13).

$$a_{11} = a_{22} \frac{\nu_{21}^p}{\nu_{12}^p}, a_{33} = a_{22} \frac{\nu_{23}^p}{\nu_{32}^p}, a_{11} = a_{33} \frac{\nu_{31}^p}{\nu_{13}^p}, a_{12} = -a_{22}\nu_{21}^p, a_{23} = -a_{22}\nu_{23}^p, a_{13} = -a_{33}\nu_{31}^p \quad (14)$$

Before fibre break happens, the component ν_{21}^p and ν_{31}^p equal zero due to the linear behavior in fibre direction [15].

Without loss of generality setting $a_{22} = 1$ and substituting Eqs.(14) into Eq.(1) gives the yield criterion as

$$2f = \frac{\nu_{21}^p}{\nu_{12}^p} \sigma_{11}^2 + \sigma_{22}^2 + \sigma_{33}^2 - 2\nu_{21}^p \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} - 2\nu_{23}^p \sigma_{22} \sigma_{33} - 2\nu_{31}^p \sigma_{11} \sigma_{33} + 2a_{44} \sigma_{12}^2 + 2a_{55} \sigma_{13}^2 + 2a_{66} \sigma_{23}^2 \quad (15)$$

From Eqs.(3)-(6) we can derive

$$(d\bar{\varepsilon}^p)^2 = \frac{4}{3} f (d\lambda)^2 = \frac{2}{3} f \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \quad (16)$$

Thus the relationship between effective plastic strain increment and plastic strain increment can be derived

$$\begin{aligned} (d\bar{\varepsilon}^p)^2 &= \frac{2}{3\Delta} [A_{11} (d\varepsilon_{11}^p)^2 + A_{22} (d\varepsilon_{22}^p)^2 + A_{33} (d\varepsilon_{33}^p)^2 + 2A_{12} d\varepsilon_{11}^p d\varepsilon_{22}^p + 2A_{23} d\varepsilon_{22}^p d\varepsilon_{33}^p \\ &\quad + 2A_{13} d\varepsilon_{11}^p d\varepsilon_{33}^p + \frac{4}{3} \left[\frac{(d\varepsilon_{12}^p)^2}{a_{44}} + \frac{(d\varepsilon_{23}^p)^2}{a_{55}} + \frac{(d\varepsilon_{31}^p)^2}{a_{66}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} \begin{cases} A_{11} = a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2, A_{22} = a_{11}a_{33} - a_{13}^2 \\ A_{33} = a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2, A_{12} = a_{13}a_{23} - a_{12}a_{33} \\ A_{13} = a_{12}a_{23} - a_{13}a_{22}, A_{23} = a_{12}a_{13} - a_{11}a_{23} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Thus the effective stress under the uniaxial normal stress σ_{ii} can be written as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}a_{ii}\sigma_{ii}} \quad (19)$$

From Eq.(12) we can derive

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{a_{ji}}{a_{ii}}d\varepsilon_{ii}^p, d\varepsilon_{kk}^p = \frac{a_{kk}}{a_{ii}}d\varepsilon_{ii}^p, d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = 0 (i \neq j) \quad (20)$$

From Eq.(17) we can derive

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3a_{ii}}}d\varepsilon_{ii}^p \quad (21)$$

With the same approach, the effective stress and strain under uniaxial shear stress can be written as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{3a_{rr}}\sigma_{ij}, d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3a_{rr}}}d\varepsilon_{ij}^p \quad (22)$$

Then the hardening law $\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\varepsilon}^p$ can be obtained from different loading conditions and different hardening law from different loading conditions must be the same. Therefore, the unknown parameters $a_r (r=4,5,6)$ can be obtained by means of trial and error optimization to the uniaxial normal stress loading conditions and the final $\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\varepsilon}^p$ relationship can be determined. The whole procedure for the anisotropic elasto-plasticity calculation and the determination of the plasticity parameters is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: A flow chart for the calculations.

2.3 Incorporation of fiber failure

Shen et al. [5, 6] found that there is a knee point on dent depth-impact energy curve and dent depth-contact force curve (Fig.2) from impact and QSI experiments on large amounts of specimens of different composite material systems. From detailed observations on damage morphology of the specimen, fiber failure was found to be associated with the knee point. When the impact energy was less than the energy corresponding to the knee point, there is no fiber failure or only a small amount of fiber failure (only in some plies) happened inside. When the impact energy was larger than the energy corresponding to the knee point, large amount of fiber failure would occur inside. Therefore, as the main reason for the knee point on dent depth-impact energy curve, fiber breakage was considered in this paper.

In this study, the maximum stress criterion was used for the judgment of fiber failure. If fiber failure occurs, the stiffness is degraded and a new group of plastic parameters is used to effect the rapid growth of dent depth when impact energy of contact force increases after the knee point. The properties of the fiber and matrix in the micromechanical model should be degraded as well.

Figure 2: A schematic figure of knee point [6].

2.4 Failure criteria and damage evolution of delamination

Delamination is the main damage form of composite structures in low-velocity impact and QSI, and it is also the main reason for the loss in energy. In this work, cohesive elements which took a bi-linear traction-separation law were used in interface to simulate the delamination.

The initial linear elastic constitutive relationship of the cohesive element is defined as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{nn} & & \\ & K_{ss} & \\ & & K_{tt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_n \\ \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where t_n is the normal stress, t_s and t_t are the shear stresses. $K_{ii}(i=n,s,t)$ are the stiffness coefficients corresponding to the three components of stress. $\varepsilon_i(i=n,s,t)$ are the normal and two shear strains, when the thickness of the cohesive element is T_0 , $\varepsilon_n = \frac{\delta_n}{T_0}$, $\varepsilon_s = \frac{\delta_s}{T_0}$, $\varepsilon_t = \frac{\delta_t}{T_0}$ where $\delta_i(i=n,s,t)$ are the normal and two shear displacement.

Damage initiation of the cohesive element is the quads stress criterion:

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle t_s \rangle}{t_s^0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle t_t \rangle}{t_t^0} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (24)$$

where $t_i^0(i=n,s,t)$ are the nominal and two shear strengths. The Macaulay bracket $\langle \bullet \rangle$ implies that a compressive normal stress does not contribute to the damage initiation.

The propagation of delamination is determined by BK criteria based on energy release rate as follows:

$$G_{equiv} = G_I + (G_{II} - G_I) \left(\frac{G_{II} + G_{III}}{G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}} \right)^\eta \quad (25)$$

$$G_{equivC} = G_{IC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II} + G_{III}}{G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}} \right)^\eta \quad (26)$$

where G_I, G_{II}, G_{III} are the normal and two shear energy release rate. G_{IC}, G_{IIC} are the critical release rate for the Mode I and Mode II fracture. In this study, the characterization of mixing degree index $\eta = 1.45$ [14]. When $G_{equiv} = G_{equivC}$, the cohesive element damages completely.

3 EXPERIMENT AND FE IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Materials and specimens

Two kinds of graphite/epoxy composite materials T300/6421 and T700/6421 were tested. The laminates were manufactured by RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process with the carbon fibre infused with resin. The material properties of two composite systems of laminates and their components are listed in Table 1. The size of the two kinds of laminates were the same as 150mm × 100mm. The stacking sequence of laminates were quasi-isotropic, with [45/0/-45/90]4s and [45/0/-45/90]3s corresponding to T300/6421 and T700/6421. As the average thickness of two kinds of laminates were the same as ~5mm, the test results of different groups could be compared with each other.

	Elastic modulus/GPa				Poisson's ratio		Strength/MPa	
	E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	G_{23}	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	X_T	X_C
T300/6421	120	9.5	4.7	3.2	0.32	0.48	1650	1048
T700/6421	125	9.8	4.8	3.4	0.314	0.45	2832	1286
T300	230	15	15	7	0.2	0.3		
T700	240	20	20	10	0.2	0.3		
6421		3.97						

Table 1: Material properties for the two composite systems T300/6421 and T700/6421.

3.2 Low-velocity impact test

Low-velocity impact tests of laminates were carried out following the test standard ASTM D7136 [19]. Impact tests were carried out on a drop weight impact test machine which could take an instrumented mass dropped from a specific height onto the center of the specimen held by a support. The supporting of specimens is a steel plate with a cutout of 125mm × 75mm. The impactor has a spherical head with a diameter of 16mm. The impact energies varies from approximately zero to almost penetrating the laminates to form a curve of dent depth-impact energy. Permanent indentations were measured by dial indicator. C-scan was used on specimens after the impact tests to examine damage inside.

3.3 Quasi-static indentation test

Quasi-static indentation tests of laminates were carried out following the test standard ASTM D6264 [20]. The specimens were indented by a spherical head of the same diameter as the impactor of impact tests and supported by the same holder of impact tests. The specimens were loaded at the center by a testing machine with the loading velocity of 1mm/min. Dial indicator and C-scan were also used on a specimen after unloaded to measure permanent indentations and examine damage inside.

3.4 Micromechanical analysis to determine the plasticity parameters

A cubic RVE (representative volume element) model was established in ABAQUS for micromechanical to determine the plasticity parameters. The fiber volume ratio can be accounted for in the RVE. In RVE model, the macro plasticity of the material is reflected in the matrix as the fiber is assumed to be linear elastic with transverse isotropy and the matrix is isotropically elastic-plastic. The material parameters of the fiber and the matrix is listed in Table 1. The fiber volume fraction is 60%. A linear hardening law is employed to describe the uniaxial plastic stress-plastic strain relationship as follows:

$$\varepsilon^p = a(\sigma - \sigma_y) \quad (27)$$

the parameter σ_y for matrix 6421 was tested as 79 MPa, a is assumed to be $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$.

According to the method established by Sun et al. [16-18], the RVE model under uniaxial loading conditions including longitudinal tension ($\sigma_{11} \neq 0$), transverse tension ($\sigma_{22} \neq 0$), longitudinal shear ($\tau_{12} \neq 0$) and transverse shear ($\tau_{23} \neq 0$) are needed to be performed. When applying boundary conditions, the compatibility condition that each RVE deforms identically, and each side face the RVE remains plane and normal to its initial after deformation should be satisfied.

The plasticity parameters of T300 and T700 are the same because of the same plastic behavior of the matrix which are listed in Table 2.

(a) Before fiber breakage	
Coefficients in the yield function	$a_{11}=0, a_{22}=a_{33}=1, a_{12}=a_{13}=0, a_{23}=-0.5, a_{44}=a_{66}=5.0, a_{55}=6.8$
Parameters in the hardening law	$A_1=2.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ MPa}^{-1.5}, A_2=1.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ MPa}^{-1.32}, n_1=1.5, n_2=1.32,$ $\bar{\sigma}'=100 \text{ MPa}$
(b) After fiber breakage	
Elastic properties of the lamina	$E_1=E_2=E_3=0.01 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}=G_{13}=G_{23}=0.005 \text{ GPa},$ $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=\nu_{23}=0.001$
Coefficients in the yield function	$a_{11}=a_{22}=a_{33}=0.667, a_{12}=a_{13}=a_{23}=-0.333, a_{44}=a_{66}=a_{55}=1$
Parameters in the hardening law	$A_1=5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ MPa}^{-1.8}, A_2=9.1 \text{ MPa}^{-1.5}, n_1=1.8, n_2=1.5, \bar{\sigma}'=0.2 \text{ MPa}$

Table 2: Plasticity parameters for T300/6421 and T700/6421.

3.5 Finite element model

A finite element model according to tests (Fig.3) was established in ABAQUS in this work. The dynamic solver ABAQUS/Explicit was used to simulate the impact and indentation process. The 8- node isoparametric brick elements were used in the modeling of the composite laminates. The anisotropic elasto-plastic material model incorporating fiber failure had been implemented in the user-defined subroutine VUMAT. Cohesive elements COH3D8 were used in interlaminar to simulate the delamination. Interface parameters for T300 and T700 were listed in Table 3.

The Rayleigh damping $\mathbf{C} = \alpha \mathbf{M} + \beta \mathbf{K}$ was adopted to eliminate the residual oscillations of plate after the ending of the impact process. The numbers of coefficients are $\alpha = 3000, \beta = 10^{-7}$ according to Ref [14].

The general contact algorithm available in ABAQUS/Explicit was used to simulate contact in the model. Such an algorithm generates contact forces resisting node-into-node, node-into-face, node-into-analytical surface and edge-into-edge contact penetrations which may arise in the model including ply contact of initially nonadjacent plies.

Figure 3: Finite element models.

	Elastic modulus (GPa/mm)		Interlaminar strength (MPa)		Interlaminar fracture toughness (N/mm)	
	K_{nn}	$K_{ss} = K_{tt}$	t_n^0	$t_s^0 = t_t^0$	G_{IC}	$G_{IIC} = G_{IIIc}$
T300/6421	750	372	60	80	0.2	0.7
T700/6421	848	412	40	70	0.15	0.6

Table 3: Interface parameters for T300/6421 and T700/6421.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Comparison between T300 and T700 laminates

Dent depth-impact energy relationships of T300 and T700 specimens in impact test and simulation are presented in Fig.4, and dent depth-contact force relationships of two groups of laminates in QSI test and simulation are presented in Fig.5. The numerical results agrees well with the experiment results. For T300 laminates, there is an obvious knee point as proposed by Shen et al. [6] on dent depth-impact energy and dent depth-contact force curves. The comparison between test and FE results for the T300/6421 laminates before and after knee point is shown in Fig.6. According to the results, knee point is related to fiber breakage as amount of fiber breakage occurs beyond the knee point which leads to another increase rate of indentation depth to impact energy or contact force compared before the knee point. However, it is difficult to identify a knee point on those curves for T700 laminates.

Figure 4: Dent depth-impact energy relationships for two groups of laminates in impact tests.

Figure 5: Dent depth-contact force relationships for two groups of laminates in QSI tests

(a) Impact energy of 28J (before the knee point) (b) Impact energy of 40J (after the knee point)
Figure 6: Test and FE results for the T300/6421 laminates before and after the knee point

Delamination area of laminates after impact and QSI by C-scan are presented in Fig.7. For T300 laminates, delamination area increases slowly as the indentation depth increases. When indentation depth increases at 2.0~2.5mm with amount of fiber breakage occurs and the laminate is almost be penetrated, delamination does not extend to the edge of the laminate. However, delamination area for T700 laminates increases rapidly as the indentation depth increases. When delamination extends to the edge of the laminate (Figs.8 and 9), indentation depth reaches only 0.5mm without any fiber breakage occurs.

Figure 7: Delamination area-dent depth for two groups of laminates in impact and QSI tests

Figure 8: Failure morphology for the T700/6421 laminate at 80J: (a) front view of the laminate after impact; (b) side view of the laminate after impact; (c) FE result of the residual deformation of the laminate after impact

Figure 9: Failure morphology for the T700/6421 laminate at the maximum contact force: (a) test photo; (b) FE result

From the results, we can find out that impact or QSI applied energy are mainly dissipated by fiber breakage thus the range of delamination is limit inside the T300 laminates while the energy are mainly dissipated by delamination thus not any fiber breakage occurs inside the T700 laminates. As can be seen from the SEM morphologies of T300 and T700 fibers (Fig.10), T300 fiber has a rough surface while T700 fiber has a highly smooth surface. Therefore, contrasts to T300 fibers, the match between T700 fibers and the matrix is worse that the cracks are easier initiated and propagated to interlaminar as delamination. The smooth surface of T700 fiber also indicates few defects in fiber which make it difficult to break.

Figure 10: SEM morphologies of T300 and T700 fibers

4.2 Comparison between impact and QSI

	Impact energy/J	QSI applied Energy/J	Maximum contact force of impact/kN	Maximum contact force of QSI/kN	Dent depth/mm	Delamination area/mm ²
(a)T300/6421						
I-1	35		10.91		0.34	969
Q-2		35		12	1.2	1406
I-3	45		11.95		1.43	1452
(b)T700/6421						
I-4	40		12.43		0.36	4321
Q-5		40		14	0.46	4859
I-6	50		13.85		0.35	4985

Table 4: Comparison between impact test and QSI test for T300/6421 and T700/6421.

Comparison between impact test and QSI test for T300/6421 and T700/6421 laminates is shown in Table 4. When the applied energies of impact and QSI are the same (I-1 and Q-2, I-4 and Q-5), the maximum contact force of QSI is larger than the maximum contact force of impact, the damage of QSI is worse than impact. However, when the maximum contact forces of impact and QSI are the same (Q-2 and I-3, Q-5 and I-6), the applied energy of impact is larger than QSI, the damages of impact and QSI are nearly the same. Therefore, damages of QSI and impact are nearly equivalent when the maximum contact forces are the same. As the dissipation of the dynamic effect, the applied energy of impact is larger than QSI when forming the same damages inside.

In engineering practice, BVID is a kind of prominent indentation which is beyond the knee point according to the airworthiness regulations. As stated above, prominent indentation can be formed on the T300 laminates instead of T700 laminates as large amount of fibre breakage occurs after the obvious knee point on T300 laminates. According to Ref.[5], peak load of QSI test is related to the occurrence of fibre breakage. When forming a prominent indentation after impact, the maximum contact force of impact must reach the peak load of QSI and the impact energy must exceed the peak load energy of QSI. Hence, the condition of forming a prominent indentation is that the impact energy (E_i) exceeds the QSI peak load energy (E_{pl}) as follows:

$$E_i > E_{pl} \quad (28)$$

5 CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model based on anisotropic elasto-plastic theory cooperating fiber failure to predict permanent indentation due to impact and QSI was established in this study. Impact and QSI tests on T300/6421 and T700/6421 were carried out. The numerical results agreed the experimental results well. From the results, an obvious knee point related to fiber breakage could be identified in dent depth-impact energy and dent depth-contact force curve for T300. However, for T700 laminates, such a knee point could not be found and the delamination was much larger to the edge of the laminates at the end. The reason for these phenomena was found as the difference between the morphologies and the match with matrix of T300 and T700 fibers. For T300 laminates, prominent indentation formed when impact energy exceeded QSI peak load energy.

In conclusion, fiber breakage plays an important role in forming permanent indentation and the match between fiber and matrix has a significant influence on permanent indentation and damage behaviors.

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